

**PRAKLINNA VARTMA – AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE WITH MODERN CLINICAL
CORELATION AND MANAGEMENT****Dr. Aswathy S. M.^{1*}, Prof. Dr. Vijayant Bhardwaj²**¹PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalaky Tantra, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Paprola, Distt. Kangra, Himachal Pradesh.²HOD, Dept. of Shalaky Tantra, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Paprola, Distt. Kangra, Himachal Pradesh.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Aswathy S. M.**PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalaky Tantra, Rajiv Gandhi Government Post Graduate Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Paprola, Distt. Kangra, Himachal Pradesh. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18428971>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Aswathy SM^{1*}, Prof. Dr. Vijayant Bhardwaj² (2026). Praklinna Vartma – An Ayurvedic Perspective With Modern Clinical Corelation And Management. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(2), 120–124.

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ABSTRACT

Praklinna Vartma is a Vartmagata Roga described in classical Ayurvedic texts under the domain of Shalaky Tantra. The condition is characterized by moist, inflamed, and discharging eyelids with itching, burning sensation, and heaviness. Clinically, the presentation closely resembles chronic blepharitis or eczematous lid conditions described in modern ophthalmology. Contemporary management often relies on topical antibiotics, steroids, and lid hygiene, which provide symptomatic relief but may not prevent recurrence. Ayurveda offers a comprehensive understanding of Praklinna Vartma through detailed descriptions of Nidana, Samprapti, Lakshana, and Chikitsa, addressing the disease at its root. The present paper aims to conceptualize Praklinna Vartma based on classical Ayurvedic literature, correlate it with modern clinical entities, and review the holistic management principles described in Ayurveda, including Shodhana, Shamana, and local therapeutic measures.

KEYWORDS: Praklinna Vartma, Blepharitis, Vartmagata Roga, Shalaky Tantra.**INTRODUCTION**

Eyelid disorders constitute a significant proportion of ophthalmic complaints due to their constant exposure to environmental factors. In modern ophthalmology, blepharitis is defined as a chronic inflammatory condition of the eyelid margins, often associated with crusting, discharge, itching, redness, and irritation. It is commonly recurrent and difficult to manage definitively.

According to Acharya Sushruta^[1], Yogaratnakara^[2] and Bhavaprakasha^[3] there are 21 vartma gata rogas. But on contrary, Vagbhata, Madhavanidana and Sharangdhara^[4] have mentioned 24 Vartmagata rogas. Praklinna vartma is mentioned as a kapha dominant disorder of the eyelids. The disease Praklinna Vartma is not described in Ashtanga Hridaya. Acharya describes another disease namely “Kaphotklishta Vartma”^[5], in which there will be Vartma Stambha, Kleda & Upacheda due to predominance of Kapha Dosha. This disease has been mentioned under the 18 Pilla Rogas^[6] due to its Deerghakalanubandhinatwa ie, chronicity of the disease.

In Praklinna vartma as mentioned in literature it was found that the disease having almost similar character to that of Kaphotklishta Vartma. So Praklinna vartma can also be included under Pilla Roga.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To review the concept of Praklinna Vartma from classical Ayurvedic texts.
- To understand the Nidana, Samprapti, and Lakshana of Praklinna Vartma.
- To establish correlation between Praklinna Vartma and blepharitis.
- To compile and review Ayurvedic management principles for Praklinna Vartma.

PRAKLINNA VARTMANiruktee^[7]

The word ‘Pra’ means excess and ‘Klinna’ means which is having Kleda i.e. Ardrata (moisture) indicating excessive moisture of the eyelids.

Nidana: (Etiology, predisposing factors)

The causative factors of eye diseases mentioned by different Samhitas are summarized as.

- Aharaja
- Viharaja
- Mansika

- Aaghataja

The causes of all eye diseases are attributed mainly to vitiated pitta, supplemented by Vayu and Shleshma. The Ayoga, Atiyoga and Mithyayoga of Indriyas are described as the causative factors for eye diseases.

Table no. 1.

S.NO.	CAUSATIVE FACTORS	Ch.	Su.	A.H.	M.N.	B.P.	Y.R.
	Aharaja (Dietary causes)						
1	Excessive use of vinegar and sour gruels	-	+	-	-	+	-
2	Kulatha and masha pulses	-	+	-	-	+	-
3	Excessive intake of fluids in night	-	-	+	+	-	+
4	Excessive intake of alcohol	-	-	+	+	-	+
5	Excessive use of madhura rasa	+	-	+	-	-	-
	Viharaja (Regimental)						
6	Diving into water immediately after exposure to heat	-	+	+	+	+	+
7	Excessive looking at distant objects	-	+	+	+	+	+
8	Sleep during day/ awakening at night	-	+	+	+	+	+
9	Excessive sexual intercourse	-	+	+	+	+	+
10	Excessive perspiration	-	+	+	+	+	+
11	Smoking or working in smoke	-	+	+	+	+	+
12	Suppression of or excessive vomiting	-	+	+	+	+	+
13	Suppression of tears	-	+	+	+	+	+
14	Excessive indulgence in fine work	-	+	+	+	+	+
15	Perverted seasons	-	-	+	+	-	+
16	Travelling in very high-speed vehicle	-	-	-	-	+	-
17	Working in dusty surroundings	-	-	-	+	+	+
	Manasika (Psychological)						
18	Excessive weeping	-	+	+	+	+	+
19	Anger/grief	-	+	+	+	+	+
	Abhigataja (Traumatic)						
20	Head injury	-	+	+	+	+	+

Samprapti

Vagbhattacharya describes the Samprapti of Vartmagata roga as follows, the Dosha Prakopaka Karana especially those which are Achakshusya and Tiktoshnaadi Ahitkar

Ahara Vihar causes vitiation of Doshas, dominantly itta circulates through vessels to the different parts of eye and different types of diseases results.^[8]

Poorvarupa^[9]

Specific Purvaroopas of Praklinna vartma is not mentioned. Acharyas have described common purvaroopas for netra rogas which are as follow.

- Guru - Heaviness of lids
- Kandu - Itching sensation
- Toda - Pricking sensation
- Upadeha - Sticking of eyelids due to organized discharges
- Aavila - Dirty eye with discharge
- Sasamrambha - Angry look with watery eyes
- Ushna - Burning sensation
- Raga - Hyperemia
- Sashulam - Pain in eyelids
- Vartmakosheshu shookapurnabham - Foreign body sensation inside the eyelids
- Vihanya manam rupam - Visual disturbances
- Kriya hani- Difficulty in opening and closing of lids

Rupa^[10]

- Arujam - Painless/Mild pain
- bahyatah shunam - swelling in the external aspect of eyelid
- Antah Klinnam - sticky exudation in inner part of eyelid
- Srava – discharge
- Kandu – itching sensation
- Toda – pricking sensation

Acharya Vagbhata has not mentioned disease Praklinna vartma instead he has described a disease named Kaphotklishta Vartma which has similar features such as Vartma Stambha, Kleda and Upadeha due to predominance of Kapha Dosha. It is considered one among the 18 Pilla Rogas.

Table no. 2: Comparison chart of the characteristic features of Praklinna vartma according to different Acharyas are.

Character	Su. Sam.	As. Hr.	YR	Ma. Ni.
Shunam	+	-	+	+
Srava	+	-	-	+
Kandu	+	-	-	+
Toda	+	-	-	+
Aruja	+	-	+	+

Prognosis – Kaphaja Sadhya and Ashastrakriya Vyadhi.

Chikitsa

General principle of treatment

According to Acharya Sushruta, avoiding the etiological factors and mitigation of vata etc Dosas are the general principle of treatments of Netrarogas.^[11]

He also opines that after noticing the possibility of development of diseases according to the aggravated Dosa, appropriate treatments should be adopted quickly, otherwise eye diseases will become severe.^[12]

Specific treatment

After eliminating the aggravated dosas through oleation and other therapies and obtaining satisfaction, the physician should treat Praklinna vartma by use of Pariseka, Anjana and Nasya.^[13]

Aschyotana

Aschyotana or eye drops may be instilled with the decoction of Musta, Haridra, Madhuka, Priyangu, Sidhartha, Rodhra, Utpala and Sariva.^[14]

Anjana

1. A collyrium (Anjana) prepared from Rasanjana and honey can be used in Praklinna vartma.^[15]
2. Leaves and fruits of Amalaka are boiled in water and Rasakriya (thick decoction) prepared and used as collyrium.^[16]
3. Roots of Bamboo are boiled in copper vessel, thick decoction is prepared and made into wicks, this can also be used as collyrium.
4. Alternatively, thick decoction prepared by boiling Triphala, or flowers of Palasha or Apamarga may be used as Anjana.^[17]
5. A compound called Yoganjana is useful in the treatment of Praklinna vartma and is prepared from Kasisa, Samudraphena, Rasanjana and the buds of Chameli rubbed and pasted with honey and used as a collyrium.^[18]
6. Excreta of goat and waste (slag) of copper wire are burnt to ashes, then added with Marica and macerated in goats' milk should be used as Pratyjanjana (pacifying collyrium); similarly, that prepared with powder (ash) of copper may be used.^[19]
7. Samudraphena, Lavanottama (saindhava), Shankha (conch), Mudga, seeds of Shigru -these together made into nice powder and used as Churmanjana (powdery collyrium) cures sluggishness, itching and also Aklinna vartma quickly.^[20]
8. Kajjala macerated with ghee and Tuttha on a copper vessel should also be used as Anjana in Praklinna vartma.^[21]

In Pillavastha of the disease treatment advised for Pilla Rogas can be given. Procedures are given like Lekhana, Raktamokshana, Virechana should be done repeatedly in order to alleviate the Doshas. Different types of Ashchyotana, Anjana, Nasya, and Dhumpana are also advised for regular use.^[22]

CORELATION BETWEEN PRAKLINNA VARTMA AND BLEPHARITIS

Praklinna Vartma described in classical Ayurvedic texts shows a close resemblance to blepharitis as understood in modern ophthalmology with respect to etiology, clinical features, chronicity, recurrence, and response to treatment. The correlation between the two conditions can be established as follows.

Correlation of Disease Entity

Praklinna Vartma is recognized in Ayurveda as an independent disease entity under Vartmagata Rogas, predominantly involving Kapha Dosha with secondary involvement of Pitta and Rakta. Similarly, blepharitis is described in modern science as a chronic inflammatory disorder of the eyelid margins, affecting the ocular surface and producing persistent discomfort and irritation. Both conditions are characterized by a long-standing course with frequent recurrences, indicating a close conceptual similarity.

Correlation of Clinical Features (Lakshana)

The classical symptoms of Praklinna Vartma correlate well with the clinical manifestations of blepharitis.

Aruja (mild pain) corresponds to the mild soreness and discomfort experienced in blepharitis. Bahyatah Shunam (external swelling) is comparable to the thickening and swelling of eyelid margins observed clinically.

Antah Klinnam (internal moistness) reflects the greasy, moist eyelid margins seen in seborrheic blepharitis. Srava (discharge) correlates with crusting, sticky discharge, and watering of the eyes.

Kandu (itching) is one of the most common complaints in blepharitis.

Nistoda (pricking sensation) corresponds to the foreign body sensation and irritation reported by patients.

Correlation of Chronicity and Recurrence

Ayurveda describes Praklinna Vartma as a chronic disease with recurrent episodes, attributed to the persistence of vitiated Doshas in a latent or Shukta Avastha. When favourable conditions or aggravating factors arise, these dormant Doshas become active, resulting in recurrence of the disease.

Blepharitis is similarly recognized as a chronic, relapsing condition in modern medicine. Despite symptomatic relief with treatment, flare-ups are common, necessitating repeated and prolonged therapy. This similarity in disease behavior strongly supports the correlation between the two entities.

Correlation of Etiopathogenesis (Samprapti)

In Praklinna Vartma, vitiated Kapha Dosha leads to Kleda and Srava, while Pitta contributes to inflammation, burning sensation, and redness. Involvement of Rakta further contributes to chronicity and recurrence.

Modern medicine explains blepharitis as a multifactorial disorder involving bacterial infection, particularly Staphylococcus, seborrhea, metabolic disturbances, and poor eyelid hygiene. Although the explanatory frameworks differ, the underlying concept of chronic inflammation, secretion, and tissue involvement closely parallels the Ayurvedic Samprapti.

CONCLUSION

Praklinna Vartma, as described in Ayurvedic classics, closely correlates with chronic blepharitis. Ayurvedic principles provide a comprehensive understanding of its etiopathogenesis and management. Early diagnosis, appropriate Shodhana, and consistent local therapy can effectively manage the condition and prevent recurrence.

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